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FLAGSHIPS – Zero Emission Waterborne Transport

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Abstract

The shipping industry is facing a complete systematic change in coming decades shifting from use of conventional fossil fuels to zero-emission operations. Hydrogen, combined with fuel cells, is one of the most promising options to implement zero-emission power production onboard the vessels as water and heat are only local emissions from hydrogen fuel cells.

The FLAGSHIPS is an EU funded project which has deployed two commercially operated hydrogen-fueled vessels. The first vessel is a container vessel, named *FPS Waal*, which has been operating between Rotterdam (NL) and Duisburg (GE) on hydrogen and fuel cells since April 2024. The second vessel is a self-propelled barge, *Zulu 06*, which has operated in the river Seine in the centre of Paris (FR) since December 2024. In both demonstration cases, compressed gaseous hydrogen, produced locally with electrolyzers powered mainly by renewable electricity, is used.

FPS Waal has a total of 1,200 kW of fuel cells onboard. Hydrogen is stored in swappable 40ft containers in 300 bar (Type II bottles) onboard the vessel. On top of this, there are battery packs onboard for peak shaving and extra power. *Zulu 06*, on the other hand, has 400 kW fuel cell system installed. As the operational profile of the vessel is completely different to *FPS Waal*, as *Zulu 06* operates mainly in the center of the city Paris, the required power level is also lower. In *Zulu 06*, hydrogen is stored also in 300 bar.

These two demonstration cases have showcased that zero-emission waterborne transport with hydrogen fuel cells can be realized already today. Vessels will be demonstrated 18 months in the project, after which, shipowners aim and expect to maintain the ships in normal commercial operation.

This paper will present and discuss the key learnings in design, deployment and operation of PEM fuel cell based power train for shipping. Also, during the project, valuable information has been gathered from the classification and approval process of novel solutions with hydrogen as a fuel.

Introduction

Inland waterway transport, as the shipping industry in general, is going through a unprecedented change currently. Efforts to mitigate climate change also affect shipping industry greatly. IMO has committed to reach net-zero greenhouse gas emissions from maritime sector before year 2050 [1]. The EU has also committed to decarbonising maritime transport and an ambition of transitioning to zero-emission inland waterway transport by 2050 [2]. Improvements in hydrodynamics, optimization of operation and route, scrubbers and such conventional technologies can help shipowners in increasing the efficiency of ships and cutting down the fuel consumption. However, to reach the targets set by IMO and EU, more drastic measures are needed.

Thus, shipping industry is currently studying alternative fuels as a way to ensure compliance. Biofuels and e-fuels can be part of the solution. They can provide a solution where system level net emissions are very low and they allow the use of existing technologies and infrastructure. However, they have their drawbacks as well, such as sufficiency of sustainable biofuels and price of the e-fuels. Local pollution from the combustion of these fuels is also a concern, especially important in densely populated areas. As an option to these fuels, electric propulsion based on batteries and fuel cells offers an interesting option.

Battery-electric solutions have of course the highest well-to-wake efficiency and are often the best options. However, with higher power demands and longer routes operations with batteries is often not possible. In these cases, hydrogen fuel cells offer an interesting option. Fuel cells are a true zero-emission solution when hydrogen is produced via electrolysis from renewable energy.

The FLAGSHIPS is a European joint project which aims to deploy two commercially operated hydrogen-fueled vessels. Both vessels have gone through the process of design and deployment of hydrogen fuel cell solutions and are already operational, one in Rotterdam, Netherlands and the other in Paris, France. In both demonstration cases, swappable compressed hydrogen storages are used.

With these two demonstration cases, benefits of hydrogen-based power train in waterborne applications will be showcased. The project has also reduced the capital cost of marine fuel cell power systems significantly by leveraging knowhow from existing onshore and marine system integration activities. Project will support further evaluation of future applications as well as the development of functional prescriptive rules for hydrogen ship approval.

In this paper design requirements of the fuel cell powered inland waterway vessel are discussed as well as the FLAGSHIPS project demonstration vessels presented. Paper will give conclusions to help other actors on the field to deploy the same technologies.

1. Scientific Approach

FUEL CELL CONSIDERATIONS

With the help of FLAGSHIPS project, Ballard has developed a type-approved marine fuel cell system, FCwave. Developing a marine PEM fuel cell system involves numerous challenges and thus, important pre-condition was to rely on already proven and mature fuel cell stacks. The module integrates the latest generation of liquid-cooled fuel cell stacks,

which are result of more than 30 years of experience in fuel cells and stack modelling and design.

Deploying PEM fuel cells in marine applications involves also regulatory challenges. Collaboration with regulatory bodies from the design phase is essential for approval and future standards. During the project Ballard worked extensively with DNV GL and gained a type approval for the FCwave marine fuel cell module. Such type approval is key in order for the industry to move forward as it ensures the safety of the technology and simplifies the approval process.

With safety in mind as a priority, two controllers for the system were incorporated, one for operation and one for safety. Extra safety design choices include a hydrogen enclosure, with all the hydrogen related components to take care of special safety requirements, and other multiple safety features embedded in every part of the module, with the required redundancy in key locations.

Figure 1. Marine specific fuel cell unit by Ballard Power Systems

HYDROGEN SYSTEM INTEGRATION AND RISK BASED DESIGN

The integration of hydrogen technologies onboard a maritime or inland waterways vessel must comply with a specific set of technical specifications and safety regulations. However, at the time of the project's development, hydrogen-specific standards were not yet included in the consolidated body of classification rules for ship design. In such cases, vessel development follows a derogatory process, relying on risk-based design methodologies and close consultation with the relevant regulatory authorities to ensure a high safety level while enabling technological innovation.

A preliminary review of the literature and previous experiences with hydrogen in maritime applications (such as the MV Hydra, owned by Norled) was conducted by the design team to define the vessel's initial concept. This preliminary design was then assessed through a Hazard Identification (HAZID) process. The HAZID identified key hazards associated with hydrogen storage, handling, and utilisation onboard, such as explosion risks, leaks, and system failures, and assessed their potential impact on ship operations and crew safety. From this assessment, the concept was iteratively refined by implementing mitigation measures and re-evaluating the associated risks using quantitative techniques. These analyses included consequence modelling, frequency assessments, and fault-tree analysis, which informed critical decisions regarding layout optimization, material selection, and the integration of safety systems (e.g. gas detection, forced ventilation, and emergency shutdown systems).

At the conclusion of this iterative, risk-based design process, the final HAZID report and quantitative risk assessment, along with a comprehensive list of risk mitigation strategies and safety equipment for hydrogen risk management, were submitted to the European Committee for drawing up Standards in the field of Inland Navigation (CESNI) for derogatory validation under the existing inland waterways regulatory framework (ESTRIN). During the design process, several aspects were closely examined by the naval architects and shipowners, including:

Hydrogen storage safety, including risk mitigation measures for fire protection

In the FLAGSHIPS project, hydrogen is stored at high pressure in composite cylinders grouped within 20-foot containers and installed on the vessel's upper deck. Given the thermal sensitivity of composite liner materials and the severe consequences of a cylinder rupture followed by hydrogen ignition, a multi-layered fire protection strategy was developed. The vessel includes a fixed fire suppression system capable of detecting and extinguishing fires in technical compartments with suppressing gas (NOVEK system). Additionally, a water spray and deluge system provides a secondary level of thermal protection, shielding the container walls and the surrounding deck areas in case of fire. As a final line of defence, the storage bundles are equipped with thermal pressure relief devices (TPRDs) that activate at a specific temperature threshold to safely vent hydrogen at a controlled flow rate, preventing overpressure and reducing the risk of catastrophic cylinder rupture.

Figure 2. Test of the spray and deluge system on the surrounding of the H₂ container storage on Zulu 06

Mitigation measures for H₂ gas leaks in confined spaces.

Hydrogen's high volatility and wide flammability range (4% to 75% in air) make gas leaks in confined spaces a critical safety concern. For enclosed areas such as the fuel cell room and adjacent compartments, the design implemented a double-barrier philosophy for all hydrogen components and pipelines. In the event of a primary containment failure, leaked hydrogen would be directed to a secondary, inerted volume and safely vented to the open air through a gas exhaust system. To further prevent accumulation, the ceilings of hydrogen rooms were designed with smooth, unbroken surfaces and a slope leading toward a central gas collection point connected to a venting outlet. These rooms were also configured for natural ventilation to ensure a continuous air exchange rate that keeps hydrogen concentrations below hazardous levels.

Automation process for risk detection and shutdown of the H₂ process and FC system

To complement these passive protections, an active safety system was developed to detect hazardous events and trigger appropriate responses. A distributed sensor network was installed throughout the vessel to monitor for hydrogen leaks and fire. In enclosed spaces, catalytic sensors were used to detect low-pressure leaks by measuring hydrogen concentration in the air. In contrast, high-pressure leaks occurring in open-air environments, such as around the hydrogen storage containers, were detected using acoustic sensors capable of identifying the ultrasonic signals emitted by escaping gas. The sensor system was supplemented with conventional shipboard fire detectors (heat and smoke) and hydrogen-specific flame detectors using thermal cameras. All detected hazards, gas leaks, fire outbreaks, or abnormal conditions, could automatically trigger predefined emergency responses, including partial or full shutdown of the fuel cell system and closure of the hydrogen supply using pneumatically actuated valves. These actions were coordinated by a dedicated programmable logic controller (PLC), independently powered by an uninterruptible power supply (UPS) to ensure operability under all conditions.

H₂ leaks and gas cloud explosions in open air.

Despite the containment and relief measures in place, hydrogen released into open air still presents a risk of flammable cloud formation and explosion, especially in sensitive urban areas such as Paris or Rotterdam, where the vessel might operate. To quantify these risks, detailed simulations were carried out using FLACS software by GEXCON AS. These simulations modelled the dispersion and ignition potential of hydrogen under different conditions, considering various release rates and environmental factors. The analysis informed key design decisions regarding the placement and orientation of vent outlets, the separation of equipment, and the establishment of safety distances between hazardous areas and the public.

Figure 3. Preliminary results of H₂ gas dispersion modelling after TPRD activation in the H₂ storage.

The integration of hydrogen technologies onboard required a fundamentally different approach to ship design, one rooted in the identification, analysis and mitigation of risks at every stage. Through a rigorous iterative process, combining both qualitative and quantitative assessments, the project achieved a design aligning with the emerging expectations of regulatory bodies such as CESNI. This outcome confirms that, even in the absence of formal hydrogen standards, safe and certifiable vessel concepts can be achieved through a structured risk-based methodology.

MARINE HYBRID FUEL CELL & BATTERY POWER TRAIN

Early in the FLAGSHIPS project, differences between fuel cells and other power sources were identified. From an electrical integration perspective, fuel cells are DC power sources with varying output voltage, differing from conventional shipboard power sources like diesel engines. Fuel cells provide good power responses but should be protected from step-like load transients to maximize their lifetime and ensure reliability. Also, power idling should be avoided.

Requirements for electrical integration, operation, and protection were similar to batteries but included specific design requirements for fuel cells:

- Operation of fuel cells as single power supplying sources should be avoided. Instead, they should be paired with other power sources with fast load dynamics characteristics.
- Fuel cells will be loaded with a ramp rate of 20 kW/s.
- Fuel cell load must always be kept above 30 kW. Overload conditions must be prevented. Shipboard loads must be capable of quick load shedding in case of fuel cell overload conditions.

To meet these requirements lithium-ion batteries were selected as secondary power sources. Both FCs and batteries were connected via DC/DC conditioning stages to a common DC bus. A DC/AC power conditioning stage is used to interact with onboard loads.

As a conclusion, hybridizing fuel cells and batteries effectively meets design requirements.

2. Demonstartions

CONTAINER VESSEL

The first demo vessel, called H₂ Barge II from Future Proof Shipping, is a 110 meters long inland container vessel that is coupled with a barge. The vessel's design followed a special approval process guided by CCNR and Lloyds Register. The ship-barge convoy sails between Maasvlakte and Meerhout making two round trips every week. The ship is retrofitted with hydrogen storage containers, Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) fuel cells from Ballard and Li-ion batteries. There is no power generation from diesel engines nor diesel fuel onboard the vessel anymore after the conversion.

There are six fuel cell modules, all located in the dedicated room built during retrofit. Each fuel cell has a total rated power of 200 kW which are coupled into 3 pairs of 2 fuel cells each. Propulsion is done through an electric bow thruster (500 kW) and electric main engine (1000 kW).

Above the new technical space inside the hold there are two swapable hydrogen containers with 500 kg of hydrogen stored in each container. The hydrogen is stored under 300 bar pressure. The pressure is reduced to 10 bar pressure inside the container and distributed to the fuel cells. The exhaust air outlet is on the old position of the exhaust, aft of the vessel's wheelhouse. The hydrogen venting pipe is located at the aft of the vessel. This pipe is used for venting hydrogen from the containers in case of emergency.

Figure 4. FC and H₂ system setup on the H₂ Barge II.

SELF-PROPELLED BARGE

The second demonstration vessel, named Zulu 06 (Figure), is 55 m long, and 8 m wide self-propelled barge dedicated to urban distribution. This ship offers an alternative to road haulage to bring goods in the city centers. Thus, it helps to reduce road traffic in cities and reduce the carbon footprint as transport via inland navigation. The Zulu 06 is a ship that carries its own crane lodged in two rails for it to move forward and backward on the flat deck of the ship, allowing it to access all types of quai and berths in the city centers. The capacity of 40 t.m permits its owner to offer a large variety of goods to be transported. From pallets, big bags to small containers and almost anything that fits in this range. The boat is a day working one from Monday morning to Friday afternoon and offers a good alternative to road transportation. The concept made its debut in Belgium and has been develop afterwards in Paris and in the Lyon area.

Figure 5. Zulu 06 in centre of Paris.

Hydrogen wise, the boat is equipped with two 200 kW FCwave PEM fuel cell modules from Ballard amounting a total power of 400 kw. 300 kg of hydrogen is stored onboard in a 20ft container filled up to 300barg. Fuel ceels and hydrogen offer 40 hours of service solely on hydrogen. Both hydrogen container and fuel cells rooms are located on the deck protected from the weather but outside with the philosophy that no hydrogen can accumulate anywhere. For ensuring the safety, all containers and rooms are equipped with a variety of sensors: acoustics ones, infrared/uvs cameras, catalytics sensors, etc.

Alongside the fuel cells, the vessel is equipped with two times 45kw batteries linked with the FCwaves. When the power need is low, the batteries can deliver the minimum power required. In normal operation the fuel cells will both charge the batteries and deliver the required power to the vessel. Lastly, when the power demand is in its highest, the batteries will add to the fuel cells to reach the maximum on shorts periods of times. Also the batteries allow the ramp up from 0 to 100% to be much quicker and therefore, the response in the command is better for the crew.

3. Results

The FLAGSHIPS project deploys two hydrogen fuel cell vessels in European inland waterways, in Rotterdam and in Paris. Hydrogen and fuel cells are technically ready technology already today for zero emission waterborne transport. During the project, partners have gained a lot of experience and learnings on how to successfully deploy these technologies:

- The rule base for these technologies is still developing which causes need for case specific consideration. Thus, close collaboration with class societies and approving bodies already in early phase of the project is extremely important for design safety and growth of FC technology's acceptance.

- Careful and consistent consideration for needs of the end-users is needed in order to capture the fast-evolving industry requirements.
- Attention to service requirements regarding fuel cell systems must be paid as there are unique features in marine applications.
- Risk-based design methodology is efficient for designing innovative concepts with a lack of recognized standards.
- Pre-normative research on hydrogen safety is necessary to update existing standards to include hydrogen specific sections.
- Existing powertrain solutions can already meet the electrical integration requirements for hybrid fuel cell and battery solutions.

References

- [1] International Maritime Organization; *Annex 15, Resolution MEPC.377(80), 2023 IMO strategy on reduction of GHG emissions from ships*; July 2023;
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